

BIODEGRADABLE FILMS BASED ON PHBV/PBAT BLENDS AND HEMP FIBERS FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *Among the food packaging industry requirements, rigid hydrophobic materials are highly demanded. These materials enable the preservation of food products, preventing weight loss while maintaining the package integrity. Research focusing on using biodegradable polymers has increased in light of the growing awareness of environmental pollution and the need to replace conventional plastics by more sustainable materials. A specific area of concern is the selection of materials used in the production of food packaging products, as commonly used plastics contribute significantly to daily waste generation (Moreno et al. 2020).*

Biodegradable polymers are widely considered as an alternative to conventional plastic-based materials, as these materials would significantly reduce waste accumulation in the environment. For example, the poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) has attracted significant interest due to its advantageous performance characteristics and relatively lower cost compared to other polymers within the polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) family (Pal et al. 2020; Gupta et al. 2022). The synthesis of PHBV involves incorporating poly(3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHV) into the PHB molecule (Pal et al. 2020; Gupta et al. 2022; Meereboer et al. 2020). Blending PHBV with other materials can improve the mechanical properties and price of the final product. For instance, a low-cost biodegradable copolymer that can be used in polymeric matrices is the polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) that is an amorphous copolyester with an aliphatic-aromatic chain formed through polycondensation of 1,4-butanediol with adipic and terephthalic acids (Pal et al. 2020; Jian et al. 2020).

PBAT can be incorporated into polymer blends to promote stiffening and improve elongation at break (Larsson et al. 2016). Although PBAT is not a natural polymer, its biodegradable capability makes it a viable alternative for producing environmentally friendly materials.

*Additionally, natural fibers are renewable, cheap and eco-friendly materials widely available from various vegetal biomasses, such as, wood fibers, jute, miscanthus, sisal, hemp, and flax (Pal et al, 2020; Wu et al, 2018), that can be used to develop biodegradable packaging materials. Hemp fiber (*Cannabis sativa*), is a natural fiber with crystalline cellulose fibrils, is an interesting under-exploited biomass to be used as a source of natural lignocellulosic fibers acting as fillers in polymeric formulation (Promhuad et al. 2022). Extensively grown in Latin America, Europe, and China, hemp fiber possesses a notable content of crystalline cellulose (55-72%), lignin (2-5%), and hemicellulose (8-19%), rendering it highly appealing as a reinforcement material in polymers (Wu et al. 2018; Promhuad et al. 2022).*

This study aimed to produce biodegradable composites focused on the highest possible amount of hemp fibers, which is a low-value residue, and blending it with different concentrations of the biodegradable polymers PHBV and PBAT. With the goal of improve the processability and the hydrophobicity of the composites, natural waxes (beeswax or carnauba wax) were added. The formulations were produced by melt compounding, and films were prepared by compression molding. The concentration of the polymers used showed to be an important element to choose the hemp fiber concentration to be employed. With the waxes addition in the biocomposites, the water vapor barrier properties were improved, and also their hydrophobicity improved by up to 41% in the contact angles results. The methodology employed in this study to produce a biocomposite using a mixture of PHBV, PBAT, and the higher possible incorporation of HF has proven to be effective, generating an environmentally friendly material, with good cost-effective and desirable traits that may be suitable for utilization in food packaging.

Keywords: Biodegradability, films, food packing

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